

RECONSTRUCTION OF DRUG CRIME MITIGATION POLICIES BASED ON JUSTICE VALUES

FARMAN ¹, YUSRIYADI ² and DEDI PRASETYO ³

¹ Doctoral Law Program, Diponegoro University, Jl. Prof. Soedarto, SH., Tembalang, Semarang.

Email: farman@students.undip.ac.id

^{2,3} Lecturer in Doctor Law Program, Faculty of Law, Diponegoro University, Jl. Prof. Soedarto, SH., Tembalang, Semarang.

Abstract

Farman, 2023, Doctoral Study Program in Law, Diponegoro University. "Reconstruction of Policy for Combating Drug Crimes Based on Justice Values". This study aims to examine 1) How is the implementation of criminal sanctions policies and actions in law enforcement against drug crimes today? 2) What are the weaknesses in the application of criminal sanctions policies and actions in law enforcement over drug crimes? 3) How Reconstruction of drug crime prevention policies based on the value of justice. The research method used is the juridical-normative method with a statutory approach, a concept approach, and a comparative approach. The results showed that; 1) The policy of criminal sanctions and actions in law enforcement against drug crimes currently does not meet the elements of justice, because there are still several obstacles in its implementation, including; a) Not Achieving the Goal of Criminalization: Deterrent Effect, b) Not Achieving the Goal of Criminalization: User and Community Health, c) Principle of Costs and Results: High Costs of Criminalization and Lack of Results, d) Unclear terms abusers, addicts, drug victims have an impact on criminal sanctions and rehabilitation, e) Criminalization of parents and the community who do not report becomes less effective in law enforcement against drug eradication. 2) Weaknesses in the Criminal Sanctions Policy in Law Enforcement for Combating Drug Crimes in Indonesia, including; a) Unclear definition and status between addicts, abusers, and victims of narcotics abuse, b) abusers are subject to punishment and lose their rehabilitation rights, unless they can be proven or proven to be narcotics victims, c) are not clearly regulated regarding addicts who violate the law by addicts who are not against the law, d) Confusion of Unlawful Criminal Offenses with elements of "controlling", "possessing", "keeping", and/or "buying" narcotics, e) Not attaching importance to intentional elements in narcotic crime, f) Criminalization for people parents and people who do not report, g) Equality of Sentences for Trials and Crimes Completed. 3) Reconstruction of Criminal Sanctions Policy in Law Enforcement for Combating Drug Crimes in Indonesia can be carried out in the following ways: a) Confirmation of the Terms of Definition and Status between Addicts, Abusers, and Victims of Narcotics Abuse, b) Affirmation of Rehabilitation Rights for Drug Abusers and Drug Victims, c) Affirmation of the term drug users who are against the law with users who are not against the law, d) affirmation of the element of intent in narcotics crimes, e) affirmation of unlawful criminal offenses with elements of "controlling", "possessing", "keeping", and or "buying" narcotics, f) Elimination of criminalization for parents and the community with other methods, g) Given different punishments for probation and completed criminal acts

Keywords: Reconstruction, Policy, Crime, Drugs, Justice.

A. INTRODUCTION

Drug abuse at this time, has reached a poor condition. Drugs that were originally needed for treatment, then actually cause addiction (addiction) to sufferers or victims. One form of development of drug abuse is illicit drug trafficking. Drug crime in all its forms is one of the international crimes and endangers mankind. This concern is increasingly felt due to the widespread illicit drug circulation in society, including the younger generation.

This will greatly affect the life of the nation and the next country, because the younger generation is the successor of the ideals of the nation and state.¹

Indonesia, which was originally a transit country for drug trafficking, has now been used as a destination area for operations by international drug networks. The high rate of drug abuse is also contributed by the actions of drug syndicates.²

Statistical data accessed from the official website of the National Drug Agency of the Republic of Indonesia³ shows that reports of drug abuse cases in Indonesia are increasing. Case data handled from 2010 as many as 64 cases then increased in 2011 to 83 cases, 2012 as many as 104 cases, 2013 as many as 150 cases, 2014 as many as 384 cases, 2015 644 cases, 2016 as many as 881 cases, 2017 as many as 990 cases, 2018 as many as 1089 cases.

The decline occurred in 2019 along with the emergence of Covid-19, which was 951 cases, then decreased again in 2020 833 cases, in 2021 as many as 766. However, narcotics cases increased again in 2022 by 831 cases. In 2023, BNN revealed 768 cases of narcotics crimes with 1,209 suspects

Drug smuggling entering Indonesia from abroad is increasingly rife. A joint task force of the Directorate of Drug Crimes, Criminal Crimes, Criminal Crimes, POLRI and Customs uncovered the smuggling of 1.8 tons of methamphetamine from a Singapore-flagged ship in the waters of the Riau archipelago on Tuesday, February 20, 2018, the disclosure of methamphetamine was the largest disclosure previously, on February 7, 2018 the National Drug Agency (hereinafter referred to as BNN) seized 1.3 tons of methamphetamine from the Singapore-flagged MV Sunrise Glory.

The ship was captured by the Indonesian Navy at KRI Sigurot 864 in the waters of the Philips Batam strait of Riau Islands, suspected of smuggling from Taiwan.⁴

Methamphetamine that failed to be smuggled is only a small part of the total drugs that enter Indonesia, only 10 percent of the total that is infiltrated in Indonesia. BNN admitted that 5 (five) tons were missed through the same route by the same ship.

In 2017 BNN reported two largest disclosures, namely 1.2 million ecstasy pills from the Netherlands on July 21, 2017 and 1 (one) ton of methamphetamine in Anyer on June 13, 2017. In 2018, it uncovered the smuggling of 3.1 tons of methamphetamine originating from Taiwan.⁵

Seeing the increasing development of criminal acts in the field of drugs and the impact caused by the abuse and illicit circulation of drugs is very dangerous for the life of the nation and state, especially for the sustainability of the growth and development of the younger generation, the international community including the Indonesian nation as part of the international community began to think seriously and pay considerable attention in preventing and eradicating drug crimes.⁶

According to Barda Nawawi Arif, implementing criminal law policy means holding elections to achieve the best results of criminal legislation, in the sense of fulfilling the requirements of justice and usefulness.⁷

Efforts to overcome drug abuse crimes have two ways, namely using non-penal means or preventive measures (preventing before a crime occurs) and penal or repressive measures (efforts after a crime). Repressive efforts are all actions taken by law enforcement officials in countermeasures after a crime or criminal act, including repressive efforts such as investigation, prosecution until a crime is committed.⁸

Indonesia in an effort to overcome drug abuse has been born Law Number 22 of 1997 concerning Drugs which has been amended by Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Drugs. In addition to the law, there are also other regulations, both in the form of ministerial regulations, regulations of the head of BNN, as well as joint decisions between ministers, heads of BNN and the Chief of Police.

So far, law enforcement officials tend to impose criminal sanctions for the perpetrators of these crimes, without carrying out rehabilitation. By providing criminal sanctions in the form of imprisonment, it is hoped that perpetrators of drug abuse crimes will become a deterrent and not repeat their actions. But what happens is the opposite, the criminal sanctions in the form of imprisonment are not effective in making them deterrent from using drugs. Without detoxification through medical rehabilitation, they will return to search for drugs once they leave the penitentiary.⁹

The Indonesian Brotherhood of Drug Victims (PKNI) sees that there are still disproportionate actions by law enforcement against drug abusers. In his experience assisting drug abusers involved in legal cases, many of his clients were actually charged with Article 112 of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Drugs which essentially stored and controlled drugs so that eventually the abuser ended up in prison.¹⁰

Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Drugs mandates law enforcement, especially investigators and public prosecutors to protect, rescue and ensure drug abusers/victims are rehabilitated medically and socially. However, the average accused drug abuser/victim is suspected by Article 112 investigators, as a non-victim criminal offender and receives alternative charges or subsidiary charges or cumulative charges in the judicial process. Law enforcement, especially prosecutors, are mandated to ensure the rehabilitation of abusers through a single indictment. In addition, the Prosecutor did not make any arrests during the prosecution process for possession or drug abuse cases.¹¹

This is where the rehabilitative spirit of enforcement must be possessed by Investigators, Public Prosecutors, and Judges and the community because abusers, especially victims, are guaranteed by the Drug Law to be rehabilitated instead of imprisoned. The role of the prosecutor in the rehabilitation justice system is also very strategic for cases of abusers through a single indictment because the purpose is to protect and save (Article 4b). Then against cases of drug abuse for oneself (Article 127) and ensuring that the abuser is rehabilitated (Article 4d). The reason is that self-abusers do not meet the burden if the status of the accused is carried out in detention (Article 21 of the Code of Criminal Procedure).¹² This single indictment is a mandate of the purpose of the drug law. Therefore, the prosecutor must sort out which crimes are circulating, which are crimes of abuse, including which abusers are concurrently dealers and

which abusers have become addicts. The crime of abuse for oneself, not for sale must be covered, saved (Article 4b), and must be guaranteed for rehabilitation (Article 4d). Meanwhile, dealers must be eradicated (Article 4c).¹³

If investigators still suspect the abuser as a criminal offender who deserves to be detained and the public prosecutor charges in the form of charges in the form of alternative, subsidiary or cumulative charges, then there is an opening to arrest the abuser. This gap is still happening today. As a result, abusers lose the right to be rehabilitated and recovered and victims continue to be abusers during and after serving their sentences, even worse during their time in prison because they are affected by other inmates. This is precisely the burden on the state.¹⁴

Regarding the duty of prosecutors as researchers of drug crime investigations, especially in cases of abuse, based on Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning drugs, the preparation of charges is excluded from the criminal justice system, adjusted to the purpose of making laws. Public prosecutors must be extra careful because abuse cases are criminal cases whose defendants are guaranteed by law to be rehabilitated (Article 4c). Cases of abusers who by Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Drugs are decriminalized (acts that were initially considered criminal, then considered ordinary behavior). The accused were criminally threatened (Article 127). The forced effort is in the form of rehabilitation (Article 13 PP 25/2011), the sanction is in the form of rehabilitation punishment (Article 103/1).¹⁵

To follow up on the order of Law No. 35 of 2009 concerning Drugs, a joint regulation has been made between seven state institutions regarding the technical implementation of rehabilitation of drug abusers. The regulation was signed by the Chief Justice of the Supreme Court, Minister of Law and Human Rights, Minister of Health, Minister of Social Affairs, Attorney General, Head of POLRI, Head of BNN. The regulation was enacted on March 11, 2014. If you look at the time span between Law No. 35 of 2009 on Drugs made in 2009 and the joint regulations of the seven state institutions on the technical implementation of rehabilitation made only in 2014, then the big question is how technical the implementation of rehabilitation was before the emergence of the joint regulation of seven state institutions, or the more basic question is whether so far law enforcement officials have implemented The mandate contained in Article 54 of Law No. 35 of 2009. Because so far the tendency of law enforcement officials in handling drug abuse cases is to impose criminal sanctions only without imposing rehabilitation sanctions, this is contrary to what is contained and stated in Article 54 of Law No. 35 of 2009.^{16,17}

They need medical rehabilitation to recover their condition. When they are admitted to prison without any medical therapy, this does not solve their problems because they are in a state of drug dependence. Attempts to conduct hearings on drug users in prisons will only stop this activity temporarily. The root of the problem is precisely the existence of a large demand for drugs and the supply for it so that transactions occur.¹⁸

They are in prison in a position of drug dependence and all means will be done to obtain drugs. So far, they have not received therapy in the penitentiary to reduce their drug dependence so that their condition is still sick.

Coupled with prison conditions in Indonesia which are mostly overcapacity. This condition can make the situation worse, some prisoners who were not previously involved in drug networks may become dealers.¹⁹

It's no secret that many drug users are in prisons but are still drug dependent. This is because they are only physically detained but the disease has not been cured. They need treatment that has not been maximally obtained. Those in prisons in conditions of drug dependence should indeed get proper medical therapy and be rehabilitated so that they are not in the environment of fellow prisoners who are still drug dependent as they are today. This condition can actually aggravate their state of dependence on drugs.²⁰

The above description that the author has described regarding what has been stipulated by law regarding the rehabilitation of perpetrators involved in drug crimes, drug addicts and victims of drug abuse who are without rights and against the law as suspects or defendants in drug abuse who are undergoing the process of investigation, prosecution, and trial in court are given treatment and selection of rehabilitation institutions. The determination of the eligibility for rehabilitation is based on a court decision as contained in the Regulation of the Head of the National Drug Agency Article 3 Paragraph (1) NUMBER 11 of 2014 concerning Procedures for Handling Suspects and / or Accused Drug Addicts and Victims of Drug Abuse into Rehabilitation Institutions.

In fact, at the investigation level, there are obstacles in terms of victims' families in the awareness process of users, inadequate facilities and infrastructure both for outpatient and inpatient care, until the last internal constraints in the form of officer competence and completeness of supporting facilities using measuring instruments, policies in the form of feasibility standards for rehabilitation places so that later the goal of curing users will be achieved and there is a deterrent effect with carry out the judgment rendered by the judge.

B. RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used is normative juridical research with a statutory approach and a concept approach.²¹

1. Types of Research

This research is included in the type of doctrinal research, where the approach method used is normative juridical. The study method used in this study is normative legal research, which is a study conducted by examining certain legal problems based on the implementation of applicable laws and regulations or applied to a legal case.²²

2. Research Approach

- a. Statute approach is an approach taken by reviewing laws and regulations related to the legal issues raised.²³
- b. Conceptual approach (conceptual approach) is an approach that departs from the views and doctrines that develop in legal science.²⁴

3. Data Sources and Data Collection

The research source used in this study is the result of data collection carried out with library research data.

Secondary data are then grouped into three sources of legal materials used in this study are primary legal materials, secondary legal materials, and tertiary legal materials as follows:

a. Primary Legal Materials

Primary legal materials are data that are materials in binding legal research sorted based on the hierarchy of legislation.

b. Secondary Legal Material

Secondary legal research is material in the form of all publications on law that are not official documents, including textbooks, legal dictionaries, legal journals, and commentaries on court decisions

c. Tertiary Law Materials

Tertiary legal material, is also legal material that can explain both primary legal material and secondary legal material, in the form of dictionaries, lexicons and others related to the focus of research.

4. Data Analysis

The research technique in this dissertation is descriptive analytical, where analysis is carried out critically using various theories of research problems. The collected data is analyzed descriptively with a qualitative approach, namely by providing a thorough and in-depth presentation and explanation (holistic / verstelen) scientifically.

C. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. The implementation of criminal sanctions policies and actions in law enforcement to combat drug crimes at this time

The policy of criminal sanctions and actions in law enforcement to combat drug crimes currently does not meet the elements of justice, because there are still several obstacles in its application, including; a) Non-Achievement of Criminalization Objectives: Deterrent Effect, b) Non-Achievement of Criminalization Objectives: User and Public Health, c) Cost and Outcome Principle: High Cost of Criminalization and Lack of Results, d) Unclear terms of Abuse, Addict, Drug Victim which has an impact on criminal sanctions and rehabilitation, e) Criminalization of parents and people who do not report becomes less effective in law enforcement against drug eradication.

Narcotics abuse is a crime and violation that threatens the safety, both physical and mental of the user and also to the surrounding community socially, so with a theoretical approach, the cause of drug abuse is a material offense, while the act is to be held accountable by the perpetrator, through formal offense.

Given the dangers that can be caused in the misuse of narcotics, the prohibitions as mentioned in Article 114 paragraph (1) indicate that the law determines all acts without rights or against the law to offer for sale, sell, buy, receive, intercede in buying and selling, exchanging, or delivering Class I Narcotics because they are very dangerous. The application of criminal sanctions on countering narcotics crimes is intended to provide a deterrent effect on drug abusers so as not to repeat drug crimes again. While the application of action sanctions serves to provide treatment or recovery to drug offenders who are also considered victims of narcotics crimes to recover physically and mentally and not addicted to narcotics. However, the sanctions used in handling narcotics crimes are only applied to drug users or addicts and do not apply to dealers.

Law Number 35/2009 concerning Narcotics is a manifestation of the use of the Double Track System concept because Law Number 35/2009 concerning Narcotics not only contains related to the conviction of drug abusers but also contains related to the recovery of drug abusers. The combination of sanctions given to drug abusers is not intended to aggravate the sanctions or punishments given to drug abusers, but to provide balance in punishment. So that drug abusers are not only a deterrent to commit drug crimes but also recover physically and mentally and have no desire to commit drug crimes anymore. Although the implementation of Law Number 35/2009 on Narcotics has not perfectly implemented the concept of Double Track System, its presence as one of the manifestations of the Double Track System concept provides hope for improving the legal system by upholding a sense of justice.

2. Weaknesses in the application of criminal sanctions policies and actions in law enforcement to combat drug crimes.

Weaknesses in the Criminal Sanctions Policy in Law Enforcement for Drug Crime in Indonesia include; 1) unclear understanding and status between addicts, abusers, and victims of drug abuse, 2) Abusers are subject to punishment and lose their rehabilitation rights, unless proven or proven to be victims of narcotics, 3) Not clearly regulated between addicts who are against the law and addicts who are not against the law, 4) Confusion of Unlawful Criminal Offenses with elements of "possessing", "possessing", "storing", and or "buying" narcotics, 5) Not attaching importance to the intentional element in narcotics crimes, 6) Criminalization for parents and the community who do not report, 7) Equal Punishment for Probation and Criminal Acts Completed.

Weaknesses in the implementation of action sanctions policies in law enforcement to combat drug crimes in Indonesia include; 1) No distinction between Beginners, Addicts, Victims of Abuse and Abusers in Networking, 2) Provisions regarding the criminalization of parents and the community if they deliberately do not report, 3) Unbalanced between the criminal fine to be paid and imprisonment in lieu of a fine, 4) Rehabilitation Punishment for recidivists is not in sync with the General Criminal provisions, namely Added 1/3, 5) Punishment for Drug Abusers for Themselves and Others is Unbalanced, 6) The application of prison sanctions and fines is more dominant than rehabilitation, 7) Unclear understanding and status between addicts, abusers, and victims of drug abuse has an impact on the confusion of sanctions, fines, and rehabilitation.

One of the problems due to the many terms against drug users is the reference to regulations where Article 4 letter d of the Narcotics Law which states the purpose of the Narcotics law is "Ensuring the regulation of medical and social rehabilitation efforts for drug abusers and addicts", but Article 54 of the Narcotics Law states "Drug Addicts and Victims of Drug Abusers must undergo medical rehabilitation and social rehabilitation" so that the rights of abusers to receiving rehabilitation as stipulated in Article 54 becomes unrecognized with the threat of criminal sanctions for drug users as stipulated in Article 127

Medical Rehabilitation in question is a process of integrated treatment activities to free addicts from narcotic dependence. While Social Rehabilitation in question is a process of integrated recovery activities, both physical, mental and social, so that former drug addicts can return to socializing in community life.²⁵

Based on the provisions of Article 4 of the Narcotics Law and Chapter IX of the Second Part on Rehabilitation, it can be obtained that rehabilitation of drug users is one of the main objectives of the promulgation of the Narcotics Law. The provisions of Article 54 of the Narcotics Law are closely related to Article 127 of the Narcotics Law. It states that judges are obliged to pay attention to the provisions of Article 54, Article 55, and Article 103 of the Narcotics Law in handing down decisions. However, although it is mandatory, its implementation depends heavily on the will of investigators, public prosecutors, and judges.

3. Reconstruction of drug crime prevention policies based on justice values

Reconstruction of the Criminal Sanctions Policy in Law Enforcement for Drug Crime in Indonesia can be done in the following ways: 1) Affirmation of the term understanding and status between addicts, abusers, and victims of drug abuse, 2) affirmation of the right to rehabilitation for drug abusers and drug victims, 3) affirmation of the term drug user who is against the law with users who are not against the law, 4) Affirmation of intentional elements in narcotics crimes, 5) Affirmation of unlawful criminal offenses with elements of "possessing", "possessing", "storing", and or "buying" narcotics, 6) Elimination of criminalization for parents and society by other methods, 7) Given differences in punishment for probation and completed crimes

Reconstruction of the Sanctions Policy Action in Law Enforcement for Drug Crime in Indonesia Indonesia can be done in the following ways: 1) Must be distinguished between Beginners, Addicts, Victims of Abuse and Abusers in Networking, 2) Elimination of criminalization of parents and the community who do not report and replaced with other methods, 3) Formulation of Criminal Fines Adjusted with Imprisonment in Lieu of Fines, 4) Recidivist Punishment Added 1/3 according to general criminal provisions, 5) Criminal Adjustment for Drug Abusers for Themselves and Others, 6) Application of imprisonment or rehabilitation criminal sanctions must be adjusted to the status of drug use, 7) Status adjustment between addicts, abusers, and victims of drug abuse with sanctions, fines, and rehabilitation.

One of the problems caused by the many terms against drug users is the reference to regulations where Article 4 letter d of the Narcotics Law which states the purpose of the Narcotics law is "Ensuring the regulation of medical and social rehabilitation efforts for drug abusers and

addicts", but Article 54 of the Narcotics Law states "Drug Addicts and Victims of Drug Abusers must undergo medical rehabilitation and social rehabilitation" so that the right of abusers to obtain rehabilitation as stipulated in Article 54 becomes unrecognized with the threat of criminal sanctions for drug users as stipulated in Article 127

Medical Rehabilitation in question is a process of integrated treatment activities to free addicts from narcotic dependence. While Social Rehabilitation in question is a process of integrated recovery activities, both physical, mental and social, so that former drug addicts can return to socializing in community life.²⁶ Based on the provisions of Article 4 of the Narcotics Law and Chapter IX of the Second Part on Rehabilitation, it can be obtained that rehabilitation of drug users is one of the main objectives of the promulgation of the Narcotics Law. The provisions of Article 54 of the Narcotics Law are closely related to Article 127 of the Narcotics Law. It states that judges are obliged to pay attention to the provisions of Article 54, Article 55, and Article 103 of the Narcotics Law in handing down decisions. However, although it is mandatory, its implementation depends heavily on the will of investigators, public prosecutors, and judges.

Another problem is the use of various terms for a subject of drug use that has implications for reporting mechanisms and rehabilitation measures and their criminal impacts. Therefore, integrated assessment for drug addicts and abusers is the key to the successful implementation of Narcotics Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics. However, until now the existence of an integrated assessment team is still experiencing obstacles in the field, one of which is the difference in views of law enforcers in addressing the status of addicts in narcotics cases.

Therefore, the reconstruction of sanctions policy Actions against drug abusers in the future must be adjusted to the status status between addicts, abusers, and victims of drug abuse with sanctions, fines, and rehabilitation in order to achieve justice.

D. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion analysis, it can be concluded as follows;

The policy of criminal sanctions and actions in law enforcement to combat drug crimes currently does not meet the elements of justice, because there are still several obstacles in its application, including; a) Non-Achievement of Criminalization Objectives: Deterrent Effect, b) Non-Achievement of Criminalization Objectives: User and Public Health, c) Cost and Outcome Principle: High Cost of Criminalization and Lack of Results, d) Unclear terms of Abuse, Addict, Drug Victim which has an impact on criminal sanctions and rehabilitation, e) Criminalization of parents and people who do not report becomes less effective in law enforcement against drug eradication.

Weaknesses in the Criminal Sanctions Policy in Law Enforcement for Combating Drug Crimes in Indonesia include; 1) Unclear understanding and status between addicts, abusers, and victims of drug abuse, 2) Abusers are made punishable subjects and lose their rehabilitation rights, unless proven or proven to be victims of narcotics, 3) Not clearly regulated related to addicts who are against the law with addicts who are not against the law, 4) Confusion of Unlawful

Criminal Delik with elements of "mastery", "possessing", "storing", and/or "buying" narcotics, 5) Not attaching importance to the element of intentionality in drug crimes, 6) Criminalization for parents and the public who do not report, 7) Equality of Punishment for Probation and Crime Completed

Weaknesses in the implementation of action sanctions policies in law enforcement to combat drug crimes in Indonesia include; 1) No distinction between Beginners, Addicts, Victims of Abuse and Abusers in Networking, 2) Provisions regarding the criminalization of parents and the community if they deliberately do not report, 3) Unbalanced between the criminal fine to be paid and imprisonment in lieu of a fine, 4) Rehabilitation Punishment for recidivists is not in sync with the General Criminal provisions, namely Added 1/3, 5) Punishment for Drug Abusers for Themselves and Others is Unbalanced, 6) The application of prison sanctions and fines is more dominant than rehabilitation, 7) Unclear understanding and status between addicts, abusers, and victims of drug abuse has an impact on the confusion of sanctions, fines, and rehabilitation.

Reconstruction of the Criminal Sanctions Policy in Law Enforcement for Drug Crime in Indonesia can be done in the following ways: 1) Affirmation of the term understanding and status between addicts, abusers, and victims of drug abuse, 2) affirmation of the right to rehabilitation for drug abusers and drug victims, 3) affirmation of the term drug user who is against the law with users who are not against the law, 4) Affirmation of intentional elements in narcotics crimes, 5) Affirmation of unlawful criminal offenses with elements of "possessing", "possessing", "storing", and or "buying" narcotics, 6) Elimination of criminalization for parents and society by other methods, 7) Given differences in punishment for probation and completed crimes

Reconstruction of the Sanctions Policy Action in Law Enforcement for Drug Crime in Indonesia Indonesia can be done in the following ways: 1) Must be distinguished between Beginners, Addicts, Victims of Abuse and Abusers in Networking, 2) Elimination of criminalization of parents and the community who do not report and replaced with other methods, 3) Formulation of Criminal Fines Adjusted with Imprisonment in Lieu of Fines, 4) Recidivist Punishment Added 1/3 according to general criminal provisions, 5) Criminal Adjustment for Drug Abusers for Themselves and Others, 6) Application of imprisonment or rehabilitation criminal sanctions must be adjusted to the status of drug use, 7) Status adjustment between addicts, abusers, and victims of drug abuse with sanctions, fines, and rehabilitation.

Some suggestions that can be submitted based on research results are as follows:

1. Revision of Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics relating to the formulation of criminal sanctions and action sanctions
2. Balancing imprisonment in lieu of fines so that subsidiary provisions are effective to overcome overcapacity that occurs in prisons.
3. Removing and replacing the criminalization of society, parents who do not report. The threat of criminal sanctions, confinement, and fines for violations of the obligation to

report committed by the parents or family of the addict can be said to be disproportionate and should be used in other ways to motivate the participation of parents and family

4. Clarify and reinforce the distinction between the definitions of the terms addict, abuser, and victim of drug abuse as well as affirmation of drug abuse for oneself and others that have an impact on sanctions and rehabilitation.
5. The placement of drug abusers/users with prison sanctions must be balanced with criminal sanctions in the form of rehabilitation to be carried out through medical rehabilitation and social rehabilitation.

Notes

- 1) H. Siswanto. S, *Legal Politics in Law Drug (Law Number 35 of 2009)*, First printing, (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta, Jakarta, 2012), p, 43
- 2) Bayu Puji Hariyanto, "Prevention and Eradication of Drug Trafficking in Indonesia", *Journal of Daulat Hukum* ISSN: 2614-560X 1, No. 1 (2018): 202.
- 3) BNN, "Drug Case Statistics Data", <https://puslitdatin.bnn.go.id/portfolio/data-statistik-kasus-narkoba/> retrieved February 5, 2021.
- 4) *Jogja Daily* published on Wednesday, February 21, 2018 Retrieved 2 September 2021.
- 5) BNN RI, "Health Research on the Impact of Abuse Drug," Research Center for Data and Information Agency Drug National, 2019.
- 6) Yandi Maryandi, "Death Penalty for Drug Convicts According to Positive Law and Islamic Penal Law," *TAHKIM, Civilization and Islamic Law* 3, no. 2 (2020): 59–78.
- 7) Barda Nawawi Arief, *Potpourri of Criminal Law Policy: Development of the Drafting of a New Criminal Code*. 7th printing (Jakarta: Kencana Prenamedia Group, 2014), p. 51.
- 8) Susanto, I.S. *Criminology*. Faculty of Law (Semarang: Diponegoro University, 1995), p. 118.
- 9) Ni Putu Nita Mutiara Sari and Suatra Putrawan, "Legal Regulation of Criminal Acts Drug As a transnational crime in the Southeast Asian region," *Law Journal*, 2016, 1–15.
- 10) Djisman Samosir, *The Function of Prison Crime in the Penal System in Indonesia* (Bandung: Bina Cipta, 1992), p. 67.
- 11) Maryandi, "Death penalty for drug convicts according to positive law and Islamic penal law."
- 12) *Body Drug National P4GN Extension Officer Guidelines* (Jakarta: BNN, 2009), p. 22.
- 13) *Body Drug National Norms, Standards, and Procedures (NSP) for Community Empowerment*. (Jakarta: BNN, 2019), p. 16.
- 14) Ahmad KR Basri, *Implementation of rehabilitation for addicts and victims of abuse Drug In Yogyakarta* (Yogyakarta: UII, 2016), p. 34.
- 15) Gatot Supramono, *Indonesian Drug Law* (Jakarta: Djambatan, 2007), p. 156.
- 16) M.R Hidayat, "Prevention and Control of Drug Abuse and Illicit Circulation," *Legal Dynamics* 25, no. 12 (2019).
- 17) Habli, "BNN's Authority in Handling Criminal Acts Drug by Law Drug Number 35 of 2009," *Uniska Law* 2, no. 1 (2009): 88–98, <https://doi.org/10.1038/132817a0>.

- 18) Yasmin Indahnesia Susilo and I Komang Suka'arsana, "Criminal Use Drug Group I without rights and against the law and the criminal act of circulating Drug Group I (Case Study of Decision No. 150/PID. SUS/2017/PN UNR)," *Law and Judiciary* 2, no. 1 (2017): 100–115.
- 19) R Atmasasmita, *Criminal Drug Transnational in the Indonesian Criminal Law System* (Bandung: Citra Aditya Bhakti, 1997), p. 32.
- 20) I Wayan Wardana, "Death Penalty Formulation Policy in Criminal Acts Drug in Indonesia," *IUS Journal of Law and Justice Studies* II, no. 5 (2014): 266–67.
- 21) Peter Mahmud Marzuki, *Legal Research*, (Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group, 2008), p. 95.
- 22) Soerjono Soekanto and Sri Mamudji, *Normative Legal Research, A Brief Review*, Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada, 2011.
- 23) Jhonny Ibrahim, "Theory and Research Method of Normative Law Bayu Media" (Surabaya, 2015).
- 24) Ani Purwati, "Legal Research Methods Theory & Practice" (Jakad Media Publishing, 2020).
- 25) General Provisions of Law No. 35 of 2009 article 1 (16) and (17)
- 26) General Provisions of Law No. 35 of 2009 article 1 (16) and (17)

Bibliography

- 1) H. Siswanto. S. 2012. *Legal Politics in Drug Law (Law Number 35 of 2009)*, First Printing. Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta.
- 2) Bayu Puji Hariyanto. 2018. "Prevention and Eradication of Drug Trafficking in Indonesia". *Journal of Law Sovereignty* ISSN: 2614-560X 1 , no. 1 (2018): 202.
- 3) BNN. 2021. Statistical Data on Drug Cases. Retrieved on <https://puslitdatin.bnn.go.id/portfolio/data-statistik-kasus-narkoba/>.
- 4) Harian Jogja published on Wednesday, February 21, 2018, retrieved September 2, 2021.
- 5) BNN RI. 2019. *Health Research on the Impact of Drug Abuse*. Jakarta: National Drug Agency Data and Information Research Centerl.
- 6) Yandi Maryandi. 2020. *Death penalty for drug convicts according to positive law and Islamic penal law*. TAHKIM, *Islamic Civilization and Law* 3, no. 2 (2020): 59–78.
- 7) Barda Nawawi Arief. 2014. *Potpourri of Criminal Law Policy: Development of the Drafting of a New Criminal Code. 7th printing*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenamedia Group.
- 8) Susanto, I.S. 1995. *Criminology. Faculty of Law*. Semarang: Diponegoro University.
- 9) Ni Putu Nita Mutiara Sari and Suatra Putrawan. 2016. "Legal Regulation of Drug Crimes as Transnational Crimes in Southeast Asia Region," *Journal of Law*, 2016, 1–15.
- 10) Djisman Samosir. 1992. *The Function of Prison in the Penal System in Indonesia*. Bandung: Bina Cipta.
- 11) National Drug Agency. 2009. *P4GN Extension Officer Guidelines*. Jakarta: BNN.
- 12) National Drug Agency. 2019. *Norms, Standards, and Procedures (NSP) for Community Empowerment*. Jakarta: BNN.
- 13) Ahmad KR Basri. 2016. *Implementation of Rehabilitation for Addicts and Victims of Drug Abusers in Yogyakarta*. Yogyakarta: UII.
- 14) Gatot Supramono. 2007. *Indonesian Drug Law*. Jakarta: Djambatan.

- 15) M.R Hidayat. 2019. "Prevention and Prevention of Drug Abuse and Illicit Trafficking," *Legal Dynamics* 25, no. 12 (2019).
- 16) Habli. 2019. "BNN's Authority in Handling Drug Crimes According to Drug Law Number 35 of 2009," *Uniska Law* 2, no. 1 (2009): 88–98, <https://doi.org/10.1038/132817a0>.
- 17) Yasmin Indahnesia Susilo and I Komang Suka'arsana. 2017. "The Crime of Using Class I Drugs Without Rights and Against the Law and the Crime of Distributing Class I Drugs (Case Study of Decision Number 150/PID. SUS/2017/PN UNR)," *Law and Justice* 2, no. 1 (2017): 100–115.
- 18) R Atmasasmita. 1997. *Transnational Drug Crime in the Indonesian Criminal Law System*. Bandung: Citra Aditya Bhakti.
- 19) I Wayan Wardana. 2014. "Death Penalty Formulation Policy in Drug Crimes in Indonesia," *IUS Journal of Law and Justice Studies* II, no. 5 (2014): 266–67.
- 20) Peter Mahmud Marzuki. 2008. *Legal Research*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.
- 21) Soerjono, Soekanto and Sri Mamudji. 2011. *Normative Legal Research, A Brief Review*. Jakarta : Raja Grafindo Persada.
- 22) Jhonny Ibrahim. 2015. "Normative Legal Theory and Research Methods". Surabaya: Bayu Media.
- 23) Ani Purwati. 2020. "Legal Research Methods, Theory & Practice". Surabaya: Jakad Media Publishing.
- 24) General Provisions of Law No. 35 of 2009 article 1 (16).
- 25) General Provisions of Law No. 35 of 2009 article 1 (17).